

Codes of Ethics Can be Unethical

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Abstract

The average person might assume that codes of professional ethics are themselves ethical. Indeed, one would expect such codes to be beacons of light that provide clear-cut guidance on ethical rules of conduct. Unfortunately, the facts can be quite different than the perceptions. Ethics codes can be used to perpetuate unethical practices like price-fixing, monopoly and restraints on trade. They can be self-serving tools that some profession uses to feather the nests of its members at the expense of the general public. Economists refer to this practice as rent-seeking.

The author discusses the fact that codes of ethics have been used in the past to protect members of the profession rather than the public interest and cites examples.

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restraints on trade. They can be self-serving tools that some profession uses to feather the nests of its members at the expense of the general public. Economists refer to this practice as rent-seeking.

The English language literature has been discussing these issues for years, although most of what has been published has taken a defensive position to protect the status quo.² The organizations that have codes of ethics also have journals and it is difficult or impossible to publish in one of these professional journals if one submits an article that criticizes the code of ethics of that organization.³ One purpose of this article is to highlight the problem in a way that would not be possible in a journal that is published by one of these professional accounting organizations.

In this article I will mostly be discussing the AICPA's Code of Professional Conduct, its predecessors and state clones,⁴ although many of the comments I make would be equally applicable to the codes of ethics of other professional groups, whether in accounting, law, medicine or other professions.⁵

² Codes of ethics are being developed by professional accounting organizations in the CIS, Eastern Europe and other emerging economies but the English language literature on this topic is not readily available to practitioners in these countries. It is likely that the codes of ethics that are developed in these countries will also have attributes of rent-seeking, since that seems to be the tendency everywhere.

³ One article that did manage to get published, although not in a journal that is controlled by a professional accounting organization, is Lee D. Parker, *Professional Accounting Body Ethics: In Search of the Private Interest*, 19 ACCOUNTING, ORGANIZATIONS AND SOCIETY 507-525 (1994). Another article, which is not quite as critical as Parker's, is Allison Collins and Norm Schultz, *A Critical Examination of the AICPA Code of Professional Conduct*, 14 BUSINESS ETHICS 31-41 (1995).

⁴ The various state accounting organizations have their own codes of ethics which often closely parallel the AICPA's Code of Professional Conduct. Sometimes these ethical rules are imbedded into legislation. Thus, I will also refer to legislation that has been struck down.

⁵ It has been argued that since the AICPA's Code of Conduct only applies to members, anyone who does not want to follow the Code's provisions need only

The main criticism of professional codes of ethics is that their provisions are often aimed at protecting the private interests of their members rather than the public interest. What makes matters worse is that these codes are held up as being issued to protect the public interest, which is itself a form of deceptive advertising. In a study of the Australian accounting profession spanning nearly 100 years, the researcher found that most ethical pronouncements and debates had the primary rationale of protecting the profession rather than the general public.⁶ One study found that, over a thirteen-year period, the Australian accounting profession prosecuted accountants 307 times for offenses that were of a private interest nature, compared to only 211 offenses that were of a public interest nature.⁷ A look at the AICPA's various codes of ethics and those of the state CPA societies also find that many of the provisions are of a self-serving nature.⁸

Some ethical code provisions violate the rights of free speech and press. An Australian code of ethics prohibited members from criticizing a fellow member in public. At least one Australian accountant has been reprimanded from criticizing another member's work.⁹

resign from AICPA membership. But that would not solve the problem. The AICPA's rules have been held to be binding on members and nonmembers alike. Courts have used AICPA rules to determine minimum levels of performance. See DENZIL Y. CAUSEY, JR., AND SANDRA A. CAUSEY, *DUTIES AND LIABILITIES OF PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS*, fifth edition (1995), at 19, 29, 77; *Stanley L. Bloch, Inc. v. Klein*, 258 N.Y.S.2d 501 (N.Y. Sup. Ct. 1965).

⁶ L.D. Parker, *An Historical Analysis of Ethical Pronouncements and Debate in the Australian Accounting Profession*, ABACUS 126-140 (1987), as cited in Parker (1994), *supra*, at 507.

⁷ Parker (1994), *supra*, at 519.

⁸ This tendency is not limited to Australian and American accounting groups. The same has been said of groups in England and Wales. For example, see E.K. Wright, *The Institute's Role*, ACCOUNTANT 788-791 (19 June 1975), as cited in Parker (1994), *supra*, at 510.

⁹ Parker (1994), *supra*, at 519.

In the past, codes of ethics have prohibited advertising and all kinds of solicitation. Ostensibly aimed at protecting the consumer, these prohibitions had the practical effect of preventing competition, to the detriment of the consumer. In Australia, these bans were lifted mostly due to the pressure of competition from management consulting firms, taxation companies and computer software firms.¹⁰ In the United States, the bans have been lifted mostly as a result of litigation.

A Florida rule prohibited accountants from giving someone their business card unless it was specifically requested until the court struck it down as being unconstitutional. The U.S. Supreme Court struck down a rule that prohibited CPAs from engaging in direct, in-person uninvited solicitation.¹¹

He mentality of the times is summed up nicely in the following quote:

The general prohibition against advertising is accepted today without much question. To be sure, there is nothing illegal or immoral about advertising as such, but it is almost universally regarded as unprofessional.

Younger accountants are sometimes tempted to advertise or solicit, and they may suspect that the rules are a result of a conspiracy among their older colleagues to protect themselves against new competition.

Actually the rule against advertising has many sound reasons to support it. In the first place, advertising would not benefit the young practitioner. If it were generally permitted, the larger, well-established firms could afford to advertise on a scale that would throw the young practitioner wholly in the shade. Secondly,

¹⁰ Parker (1994), *supra*, at 521.

¹¹ Edenfield v. Fane, 113 S. Ct. 1792 (1993).

advertising is commercial. Professional accounting service is not a tangible product to be sold like any commodity. Its value depends on the knowledge, skill and honesty of the CPA. Who would be impressed with a man's own statement that he is intelligent, skillful and honest? Lastly, advertising does not pay. The accountants in the early days who tried it agreed for the most part that it did not attract clients.¹²

The right to free speech and free press are among the most basic human rights. Whenever some code of ethics violates these basic rights, the purpose of the code itself is highly suspect.

Prohibitions on competitive bidding have also been struck down. The Florida Supreme Court struck down such a provision as recently as 1993.¹³ Most other states had by then already dropped such prohibitions from their codes of ethics, either because of litigation or the threat of litigation. The AICPA agreed to drop this prohibition in 1972,¹⁴ but only after the Justice Department filed a civil antitrust suit that resulted in a consent decree.¹⁵ Such prohibitions have been deemed to be restraints of trade, in violation of the Sherman Antitrust Act.¹⁶

Various accounting groups over the years have tried to restrain trade by making it illegal for non-CPAs to practice in certain areas. A Mississippi law that prohibited the preparation of

¹² JOHN L. CAREY AND WILLIAM O. DOHERTY, *ETHICAL STANDARDS OF THE ACCOUNTING PROFESSION* (New York: American Institute of Certified Public Accountants, 1966), 47-48.

¹³ *Dept. of Professional Regulation, Board of Accountancy v. Rampell*, 621 So.2d 426 (Fla. 1993).

¹⁴ *United States v. American Institute of Certified Public Accountants*, CCH *Accy. L. Rep.* § 64,082 (1972).

¹⁵ MARY BETH ARMSTRONG, *ETHICS AND PROFESSIONALISM FOR CPAs*, (Cincinnati: South-Western Publishing Co., 1993), 158-159.

¹⁶ *United States v. Texas State Board of Public Accountancy*, 592 F.2d 919 (5th Cir.), cert. denied, 444 U.S. 925 (1979).

tax returns by anyone except attorneys and CPAs was struck down as an unconstitutional exercise of the state's police power.¹⁷ The accounting profession is not the only profession that tries to prohibit competition by law. The legal profession also does it. At one time, the American Medical Association tried to prohibit dentistry and chiropractic, ostensibly to protect the public.

Another restraint of trade that was imbedded in the AICPA's (former) code of ethics was the prohibition against soliciting clients from competitors. A CPA firm could not even make a job offer to an employee of a rival firm. Clearly, such prohibitions do nothing to further the public interest. They are clearly aimed at protecting the private interest of the accounting firms.

When Senator Metcalf's Subcommittee issued its final report in 1977, one of its recommendations was that the accounting profession end its artificial restrictions against advertising and the solicitation of the clients and staff of other accounting firms.¹⁸ The revised AICPA Code only prohibits false, misleading or deceptive advertising or solicitation.¹⁹

The point of all this is that one cannot automatically assume that some professional code of ethics has anything to do with ethics. In fact, it might have just the opposite intent. Based on past history and experience, it would appear that there is a high probability that any particular provision in a professional code of ethics is aimed at protecting some private interest rather than the public interest. Whenever someone advocates a change to some existing code of ethics, the presumption should be that the newly advocated provision would have the effect of protecting some private interest. Those who are charged with evaluating and voting on such proposed changes should view the language and effects of the proposed change accordingly. If the provision would protect

¹⁷ Moore v. Grillis, 39 So.2d 505 (Miss. 1949), cited in Causey, *supra*, at 93.

¹⁸ MARY BETH ARMSTRONG, *ETHICS AND PROFESSIONALISM FOR CPAs*, (Cincinnati: South-Western Publishing Co., 1993), 140.

¹⁹ Rule 502, reprinted in ARMSTRONG, *supra*, at 68.

some private interest, it has no place in a code of ethics and should be voted down. Those who would vote in favor of some so-called ethical provision are part of the problem, not part of the solution.